

Electrically programmable magnetoresistance in multifunctional organic based spin-valve devices

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Information and communication technology (ICT) is now calling for solutions enabling lower power consumption, further miniaturization and multifunctionality requiring the development of new device concepts and new materials.^[1] One of the most fertile approaches to meet such demands is spintronics which is now facing the challenge of evolving from the first generation of devices, which lead to a revolution in the information storage^[2] (GMR readheads), to devices that feature multi-operation capabilities (logic, communication and storage) within the same materials technology.^[3] Indeed, the electrical control of the magnetoresistance can provide such capabilities and is currently being pursued along several lines. In inorganic spintronics the two main approaches are the use of combined

ferromagnetic/ferroelectric materials^[4] and spin-polarized-current induced control of the electrode magnetization.^[5]

In this paper we show that an electrically controlled magnetoresistance can be easily achieved in organic devices by combining magnetic bistability (spin-valve) and electrical memory effects into an interacting multifunctional implementation.

Electrical resistive switching effects in organic based devices have recently received widespread attention^[6] and represent one of the most promising ICT applications. On the other hand, spintronic devices based on organic semiconductors have already provided significant results^[7] and device performances.^[8] Spin injection in an organic semiconductor has been recently demonstrated by two different techniques.^[9, 10] The most common device in the field is the spin-valve, in which a spin polarized current is injected from a ferromagnetic electrode into the organic transport medium and collected subsequently by a second ferromagnetic electrode. The latter acts as a spin analyzer due to the different collection probabilities for electrons arriving with different spin orientations,^[11] giving rise to a measurable Spin Valve Magnetoresistance (SVMR).

Previously we have documented the coexistence of magnetoresistive and non-volatile electrical switchings in Tris(8-hydroxyquinolinato)aluminium (Alq₃) based vertical spin valves with manganite and cobalt electrodes.^[12] Such a coexistence was recently reported for rubrene based devices with similar electrodes.^[13] In this paper we go beyond these results by demonstrating a full electrical control of the magnitude of the spin valve effect: the SVMR can be turned “on” and “off” as well as smoothly tuned between a number of non-volatile states providing a paradigmatic example of a multifunctional device. A consistent explanation of the observed behavior is presented by upgrading an existing phenomenological model for the electrical resistive switching based on trapping-detrapping effects^[14] with the spin scattering part.

The overall structure of the devices that will be shown is, starting from the bottom:

$\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{MnO}_3$ (LSMO)/Alq₃/AlO_x/Co. The insertion of an AlO_x tunnel barrier between the Alq₃ layer and the top Co electrode was found to enhance considerably the interface quality.^{[15],[16]} The Alq₃ thicknesses investigated in this paper range from 125 to 250 nm, exceeding by far the tunneling regime. The (spin polarized) carriers tunnel from the first electrode in the organic semiconductor, propagate along the whole organic channel via diffusive hopping and finally tunnel into the second electrode.

The samples were characterized between 100 K and 300 K. For the sake of simplicity and clarity we will present data at a temperature of 100 K, at which the most extensive characterizations were performed, unless stated otherwise. In what follows a negative voltage corresponds to electrons being injected from the LSMO electrode.

As mentioned above and extensively reported in literature, LSMO-Alq₃-Co devices routinely show spin valve effects.^[17] The magnetoresistance at 100K and -0.1 V voltage bias is shown in the **Figure 1a** for a typical device with a 250 nm thick Alq₃ layer. A strong spin valve effect of about 22%, with very sharp and well defined resistance switches was detected. To the best of our knowledge this is the highest MR reported so far in organic spintronic devices at this temperature: together with the sharp vertical switches, it indicates the high quality of the devices reported here and of their interfaces.^[18] As usual, the magnetoresistance quickly decreases as the measuring voltage is increased up to about 1 V.^{[17],[19]}

On the same sample, the I-V curve shows a clear electrical bistability (Figure 1b). In general, for small voltage sweeps (within about $\pm 0.5\text{V}$), the I-V curves show no hysteresis. Above a threshold bias voltage (V_{th}) a clear hysteresis on both the positive and negative branches of the I-V appears. The switching is clearly bipolar, i.e. it depends on the sign and not only on the magnitude of the bias. Indeed, starting from zero bias and going to higher positive values, the resistance switches to a lower value at a threshold voltage ($V_{\text{th}+}$). This resistance state is

retained until the bias voltage is reversed and a negative threshold bias (V_{th-}) is reached. This negative threshold is less sharp than V_{th+} , and it does not mark an abrupt change but a smooth increase in resistance. Bistability effects are well known in vertical devices containing organic semiconductors and have been observed also in Alq3.^[12] For the device in Figure 1a the V_{th+} is about 2.25 V while V_{th-} is about -0.7 V. A ten fold resistance variation characterizes this bistable switching processes. Generally, resistance variation ratios in the range 10-100 were detected on the whole batch of investigated samples.

Figure 2a shows a similar effect for a 125 nm Alq3 thick sample, where the temperature dependence of the hysteretic behavior of the I-V curves is investigated. It is evident that as the temperature is raised a lower V_{th+} is required to restore the low resistance state, resembling a thermally assisted process. In the negative branch, there is a small negative differential resistance (NDR) step at V_{NDR} as indicated in Figure 2b. This voltage is independent of temperature therefore we speculate that the process that switches the resistance towards higher values is activated by the electrical field only, suggesting a tunneling process.

In order to perform a standard investigation on the resistive switching at 100K, we carried out a series of pulsed measurements on devices with different Alq3 thicknesses. Figure 2b shows a sequence of write/read/erase voltage pulses (top panel) and the measured current (bottom panel) for the same 125nm thick Alq3 layer device. The write voltage was 2 V, and it set the device in its low resistance state; the erase voltage was -1.5 V which set the device in its high resistance state. The reading of the device was carried out at -0.1 V, and a ON/OFF ratio of 3.5 was measured. The resistive state was retained also when 0 V was applied, confirming the non volatile nature of the effect.

The most intriguing and innovative part of the investigation is the interplay between the magnetic and the resistive switching effects. To elucidate this essential point we moved the devices from one resistive mode to another by applying positive or negative programming

threshold voltages and we subsequently performed magnetoresistance measurements at -0.1 V.

Figure 3a shows the spin valve presented previously in Figure 1b before any high voltage was applied - this corresponds to the lowest resistance state and a SVMR of 22%. Next, we apply a voltage bias of -1.5 V and the device resistance increases from 362 k Ω to 4.3 M Ω . The voltage is subsequently reduced back to the measuring value of -0.1 V and the magnetoresistance is measured. A dramatic modification of the magnetic switching is clearly visible in the Figure 3b - no identifiable SV effect can be now detected (Figure 3b). We applied -1.5 V because this is the voltage needed to completely erase the SVMR. This remarkable effect is clearly reversible: the spin valve effect is recovered by moving back to the low resistance mode. By applying a positive bias of $+2.5$ V the device moves to a 671 k Ω resistance value. In this state the spin valve effect is partially restored and it reaches a value of 11% (Figure 3c). By further increasing the programming voltage to $+3$ V a 18.8% SVMR is detected at a standard -0.1 V measuring voltage (Figure 3d). We recover the full magnetoresistance intensity after the application of $+3.5$ V programming voltage (Figure 3f). It is worth noting that applying the same voltage a second time does not modify either the SVMR or the device resistance (compare Figure 3d and Figure 3e for $+3$ V). The complete reversibility of the process is finally confirmed by the disappearance of the spin valve effect upon of the application of the -1.5 V programming voltage (Figure 3g).

A similar behavior was observed in a number of devices, albeit with some resistance variations.

The Figure 3 presents clear evidences for a multifunctional operation in these spintronic organic devices: the magnetoresistance can be reversibly modified in a non-volatile manner by applying an electric field. An additional important aspect of this effect is the possibility to generate multistate switching devices, offering possibilities that go beyond the binary (0-1) case.

Numerous mechanisms have been proposed to explain the electrical bipolar switching in Alq3 and other organic semiconductors,^{[20],[21],[6]} but none of them has been demonstrated yet.

Given the rareness of a microscopical explanation to the electrical switching in such systems, we feel comfortable in using a more general, purely phenomenological model proposed recently by Rozenberg et al.^[14] which provides a good starting point and helps to explain both the resistive switching and its interplay with the spin-valve effect. Let us briefly illustrate this model, which did not actually consider the spin degree of freedom. The nonvolatile switching from the low to the high resistive state was explained in terms of charging (charge trapping) of the so called top, bottom or middle domains (see **Figure 4a**), and assuming that the interdomain tunneling amplitudes are by far exceeding the electrode-domain ones, i.e. the device resistance is dominated by the top and bottom domains. Thus this simple but very physical model could explain both the multilevel switching and non-volatile behavior observed in many experiments.

In order to add the spin transport to this model, we start from the modified Jullière expression for the magnitude of SVMR in a spin-valve device:

$$\text{SVMR} = \frac{P_1 P_2 e^{-\frac{\tau_t}{\tau_s}}}{1 - P_1 P_2 e^{-\frac{\tau_t}{\tau_s}}} . \quad (1)$$

Here P_1 and P_2 are the polarizations of the two electrodes, τ_t is the carriers transit time across the device and τ_s is the spin coherence time. The eq.1 assumes that the magnetoresistance is fully contained in the collection process (see above) and $P_1 \exp(-\tau_t/\tau_s)$ accounts for the remaining injected spin polarization after the transit to the second collecting electrode. At the low bias range used in OSVs the spin current are in the diffusion regime so that the electrons transit time is proportional to the mobility through the Einstein's relation.^[22]

Indeed the charge transport in amorphous organic materials is governed by a thermally activated hopping between strongly localized states. Assuming that every hopping event

requires the same time, we can consider the mobility to be directly proportional to the mean number of hops needed to cross the device from one electrode to the other. One can clearly see that by lowering the electrons mobility, τ_t is increased and the SVMR is consequently lowered (Figure 4a-c). At the same time, a lower electron mobility corresponds to a higher electrical resistance, and the concurrency of this two changes is exactly what we found in our devices.

We infer that the mechanism through which the mobility decreases is charge trapping inside selected domains described above. We tentatively place these domains near the bottom interface (see Figure 4), although both the top domains and a combination of top and bottom ones could be as well a possible solution. We tend to exclude the middle domain due to the observed bipolar switching which requires in principle a trapping potential asymmetry. While such an asymmetry is hardly expectable in the isotropic bulk of the amorphous organic layer, it can be easily achieved near the interfaces. For example, UPS measurements^[23] have shown a strong modification of Alq3 energetics up to 7 nm distance from the LSMO surface. This was ascribed to a order-disorder dipole transition.^[24] These dipoles can break the potential symmetry of a trapping domain close to the interface, giving rise to the required different behavior with the bias polarity.

In order to make a rough estimate of the required density of trapping sites, we performed 3D Kinetic Monte Carlo simulation by modeling the hopping with Miller-Abrahams coefficients with a N-fold way algorithm.^[25] We used a plane of neutral traps at different distances from the injecting electrode and assumed that a charged trap site is excluded from the transport together with its nearest neighbors due to strong coulomb repulsion. For example, placing the trap plane at 2nm from the injecting interface, a density of 10% lead to a double mean number of hops compared to the uncharged sample. This relatively high trap density can be significantly decreased considering that the conduction in organic semiconductors can take

place through the most efficient percolative paths,^[26] so that only the latter need to be closed.

Moreover we placed a single plane of traps, while it is not difficult to imagine that in the actual device two or even three interfacial layers could be involved.

Strong evidence for a trapping mechanism comes from the curve reported in **Figure 5**. A procedure similar to Thermally Stimulated Current measurements was followed on a device in its high resistance mode. Starting from 100 K the device is warmed to a number of different T_{max} temperatures and cooled back to 100 K for a resistance measurement. Figure 5 shows these resistances normalized to the pristine value R_0 at 100 K. We can see that the resistance decreases by about 20% by just increasing T_{max} , indicating that we are gradually removing the cause of resistance by a thermally assisted process, as it is the carrier emission from a trapping site. Nevertheless, the amount of resistance reduction is small compared to that obtained by cycling the bias at 100K and reaching the threshold voltages. On the same sample as the one Figure 5 refers to, the resistance ratio between the OFF and ON states reached by bias cycling is about 20 (not shown here). This can be explained by a major role played by an increased carrier emission rate when a bias is applied. This effect can be due to a Poole-Frenkel barrier lowering or by a phonon-assisted tunneling.

We also want to point out that a simple background resistances effect is ruled out because the change in MR is neither constant nor directly proportional to the total resistance of the device.

We speculate that the observed control of magnetoresistance can lead to attractive solutions for some standing issues in magnetic storage and more generally in spintronic processing. For example, applying either writing or erasing voltage in a cross-bar geometry it is possible to switch on-off the magnetoresistance at selected sites even if the magnetic field is applied to the whole assembly. The effect can be also used as an on-off switch of the spin polarization of current flowing along some circuit line.

In conclusion, we showed that the magnetoresistance strength in LSMO-Alq₃-Co vertical devices can be electrically tuned within a multilevel set of non-volatile states. These states are reversibly activated or deactivated with an applied voltage bias and could reflect the charging of near-interface domains inside the organic material. The magnetoresistance variation is due to the partial or total loss of the spin polarization at the collection (spin polarized) electrode as a result of the increased transit time along the device. We claim that many reported magnetoresistance values in similar devices have to be carefully reconsidered, given the fact that the voltage history of the device can affect its resistive state and its magnetoresistance.

Experimental

The bottom electrode of the devices was a 1×5 mm² strip LSMO 20 nm thick. This film is grown on a matching SrTiO₃ 5×10 mm² substrate in a pulsed plasma deposition (PPD) machine in a 4×10⁻² mbar oxygen atmosphere, with the substrate kept at 880 °C. The sample was then exposed to air and moved to the organic semiconductor (OS) deposition chamber (base pressure 2×10⁻⁸ mBar). Prior to OS deposition, the LSMO sample was heated to 250 °C for 20 min to recover its surface properties. Alq₃ layer was evaporated on top of it at a rate of 0.05 Å/s at room temperature with thicknesses ranging from 120 to 250 nm. Subsequently the sample was exposed to air and brought back to the PPD machine where a 2 nm thick AlO_x tunnel barrier was deposited at a 2.5×10⁻² Oxygen pressure.^{[15], [16]} Finally the sample was exposed to air and moved to the metals deposition chamber, where a 40 nm thick Co film was evaporated with an electron gun at a 5×10⁻⁸ mBar base pressure.

The measurements were carried out in a 4-points cross bar configuration by using a Keithley 236 SMU. The resistances of the LSMO electrodes were few kΩ and that of the Co one was hundreds of Ω for all devices, therefore we exclude any geometrical effects due the finite size of the device, as well as any contribution of the MR of the electrodes to the device MR.^[27]

The bias is applied at the LSMO electrode, while the Co is kept at ground. The magnetic properties of the electrodes are reported in ref.[18].

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Figure 1. a) I-V curve at 100K showing the electrical hysteresis of the device b) SVMR curve of the same device as in Figure 1a. Inset: Spin-Valve device scheme.

Figure 2.

a) Write/Read/Erase Cycles performed on a 125 nm thick Alq₃ layer device at 100K. The resistive state of the device was retained after the application of a 0 V voltage bias, which proves it non-volatility.

b) I-V curves for temperatures from 150K to 275K of a spin-valve displaying the bistability effect. Hysteresis are clearly visible. V_{NDR}

is the voltage at which the negative differential resistance occurs. V_{th+} is the threshold voltage which sets the device in the low resistance state, where the SV MR is recovered.

Figure 3.

Time sequence of MR measurements for the reported device. Pre-applied biases are shown in the ellipses between the graphs while measuring biases are the ellipses laying on the graphs. The sequence is indicated by the arrows. Dashed line serve as a reference for the maximum MR effect. Graphs are normalized and maximum resistance and the change of resistance is indicated above each graph. The application of a -1.5 V bias voltage sets the device in its high resistance state and SVMR is lost. By applying a sufficiently high positive voltage bias, the device is set in the low resistance state and the SVMR is recovered.

Figure 4. Intuitive representation of the mechanism, derived by Rozenberg et al., we propose for the current spin depolarization. Figure a) reproduce the scheme of trapping domains as proposed by Rozenberg. In figure b) and c) an increasing number of sites is being closed by charge trapping in the region of Bottom Domains, reducing the spin diffusion length. On the right side of each device scheme, the polarization profile is represented, clearly showing the lowering of polarization at the analyzer electrode from b) to c).

Figure 5. shows normalized values of resistance versus T_{max} . The fact that after the temperature is raised the resistance decreases is suggestive of a thermally activated process causing the lowering of the resistance.